

Towards Complex Adaptive Control Systems in Intralogistics*

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Abstract—Due to the rising importance of flexible industrial systems and the involved occurrence of complex robotic systems, the human worker has to be integrated into the system design and its implementation to retain control over changing configurations. This paper introduces a novel way of human-machine-interaction involving humans and autonomous transport vehicles for intralogistics using multi-agent systems. The presented work shows how decentrally organized robots can adapt to human workers sharing the same environment. For that purpose, each entity, also the human worker, is represented by an agent including its specific capabilities and needs. In the resulting multi-agent system, all instances share their information with each other, hence, allowing to adapt dynamically to one another.

I. INTRODUCTION

This article proposes a step towards adaptive human-machine-systems for industrial working environments using multi-agent systems. In the near future, more and more decentrally controlled autonomous transport vehicles (ATV) are used to transport load carriers in intralogistics plants like warehouses. Conventional ATV follow fixed routes and are controlled from a single instance like a control center. Here personnel can interact remotely with these vehicles to start and stop or send them new tasks. In decentralized control systems, each vehicle acts autonomously to a certain degree including functionalities like free navigation, obstacle avoidance and automatic task assignment. Furthermore, digitization is driving previously less intelligent entities and infrastructures to transform into autonomously acting participants [12]. As a result, more control functionality is moving away from control centers to the autonomous actors themselves. They make their own decisions, which may interfere with necessary safety requirements or process stability specifications. In this scenario, new control mechanisms have to be provided to the human worker to understand actual behaviors of robots as well as other machines and retain control. Actually, it is stated, that even if more robots are introduced in production systems, more personnel is needed instead of being reduced [1]. It is also stated that better

qualified personnel is needed to control and maintain robots. One can deduct, there will be more interaction between humans and robots as well as complicated control systems have to be simplified to allow a wider range of workers to be part of future working environments. A possible solution on the one hand is to implement a new strategy to be part of the control system to interact directly with these instances and on the other hand to make them aware of the human workers and adapt to their behavior and characteristics. In this paper, these two solutions are addressed by initially making the human workers a part of the multi-agent system, allowing them to communicate with ATVs and later giving the robots location information of the human to make them aware of the physical existence of the human. The personal distance of humans plays a major role in this approach, which will affect the robots behavior.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Decentralized Control Systems

In decentralized control systems, all entities like robot, machines or higher-level control systems are represented by agents, respectively programs that follow standardized design schemes allowing autonomous behavior and task completion. Their design includes properties and behaviors. They can be designed to communicate with each other in specific forms of protocol [2], to know their own state and modify it depending on sensory input and to react on environmental changes. Software agents are defined by their behavior and can show reactive, adaptive and cognitive characteristics [3]. A cluster of agents interchanging information and influencing each other is called multi-agent system (MAS). Following Weiss there exist four different architectures for agents, logic-based agents, reactive agents, belief-desire-intention agents (BDI agents) and layer architecture agents [4]. Agent concepts used in this approach are BDI agents and reflex agents. BDI agents follow specified goals based on their current perceived knowledge about their environment and their own state and consider adequate actions [6]. Furthermore, simple reflex agents react on certain conditions with a result based on the given concept. Model-based reflex agents extend simple reflex agents by an internal state, which is updated by sensors [7]. In flexible production systems (also corresponding to flexible intralogistics systems), logical agents may represent software components, which react to its environmental influences and provide transformed information like location information. Accompanied by physical agents, which extend logical agents by a technical component or a connection to an external control unit [10]. This minimalistic set of types of agents can establish a decentralized control system.

*This project has been partially funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), Germany in the project Innovationlab Hybrid Services in Logistics and has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 688117 (SafeLog).

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Cellular transport systems (CTS) have been introduced in 2011. These are further developments of systems of automated guided vehicles (AGV). The main difference is the shift of control from a single instance, which knows all states of all vehicles and controls their tasks discretely, to a decentralized and agent controlled approach (cellular transport vehicles - CTV) [11]. The main advantage is to avoid a single point of failure resulting from the loss of control and process capability in case of a blackout of the sole control instance. In addition, one gains more flexibility by free navigation capabilities of the CTV, which allows dynamic rerouting in case of obstacles or sudden change of task or goal. The CTV are controlled by dedicated agents. They consist of three layers (see fig. 1), which are hierarchically interconnected - the sensor and actuator layer, the operational layer and the strategical layer. The first layer controls the physical modules of the vehicle. The second layer is performing robot perception and control tasks like localization, navigation and collision avoidance. The third layer represents the autonomous behavior and sets the vehicles functionality into an adequate relation. At last, the software is able to communicate with other instances of vehicles and other compatible software nodes. All together, the software of a CTV can be seen as a model-based logical agent.

Jost et al. introduced, based on the Internet of Things Architecture (IoT-A) Domain Model, a layered design to connect machines, robots and humans in production and logistics scenarios using decentralized control systems and to share local information with each other to form a global understanding of the environment in a so-called context model [5]. Physical entities are considered as equal participants of a multi-agent system and can be depicted as cyber-physical systems, which are introduced in the fourth industrial revolution [12]. The physical layer enables machines and humans to be a part of the multi-agent system by using specific hardware and communication standards. In case of human entities, this is achieved by the use of wearables (e.g. smart glasses) representing properties and capabilities of the human and later feeding this information to dedicated agents [5].

B. Human-Robot-Interaction

Nowadays, there are robots working in many areas of production and logistics. They are designed to allow safe operation, which is realized by either robot-dedicated areas surrounded by safety technology or safety technology integrated in the robot itself [8]. This results in non-collaborative relations between humans and robots or process interruptions in case a mobile robot performs safety stop when a human worker is approaching. If one wants to implement human-robot-interaction, safety-specific challenges have to be overcome, especially in flexible production and logistics systems [9]. When it comes to human-robot-interaction not only the safety aspects have to be considered. In addition, social and cognitive relations are to be taken into account, if one wants to make humans and robot collaborate or at least work in the same environment. Humans may project social

Fig. 1. CTV system structure [11]

behavior learned from interaction with other humans also on robots behavior. Meaning that in case a robot is approaching, the human is awaiting some kind of social interaction or is trying to figure out if a robot is either friendly or not – in the worst-case one is trying to escape in case of infraction of the intimate zone. These interdependencies are investigated in the field of proxemics [14]. Studies have been conducted on the distance between robot and human [15] and also considering variation in types of motion [16]. To technically deal with these interrelations, the following chapter will introduce an implementation of a real-world intralogistics scenario where human workers share the same space with CTV, both parties integrated in a multi-agent system, allowing the robot to be aware of the presence of a human and react according to individual needs of the human.

III. ADAPTIVE INTERACTION IN LOGISTICS ENVIRONMENTS

This chapter depicts the examined use case scenario with the applied multi-agent system and the interdependencies amongst all agents. It shows how the system is tested and evaluated using recorded datasets from the fused absolute pose of the human worker.

A. Use Case Description

The scenario to examine includes a warehouse setup, where CTVs transport small load carriers (SLD) from a storage rack to designated stations, for example picking stations or production aisles. In addition, there are humans working at picking stations or maintenance personnel repairing machines, who are sharing the same space and are

Fig. 2. Use Case Scenario

possibly crossing routes of the CTV (see fig. 2). Since we want to have the CTV adapt to the worker, here meaning path interference or collision avoidance with the worker, the vehicles should move away from the worker according to a personal distance of the worker. In case a worker is surrounded by many vehicles that may put him in an inconvenient situation, the vehicles ought to move away from him. The CTVs are controlled decentrally by software agents, follow their designated routes and of course know their location at any time at a sufficiently accuracy. Due to uncertainties of their navigation systems, the accuracy of the vehicle can be more or less good. The humans can only approximate the precise location in the warehouse but not as exactly as the vehicle would do and naturally have no possibility to pass that information to the CTV.

To overcome this situation, the humans are wearing smart glasses - the Microsoft HoloLens in this case. There is a software agent implemented on the HoloLens, which is able to communicate with the CTV agent and offers as well as uses at least services of location exchange. Since the multi-agent system mono is used the implementation is hardware- as well as operating system independent and therefore, any device could be used. Furthermore, the HoloLens is able to identify the CTV unambiguously and to calculate the relative pose based on the CTV. This relative pose and the ID of the vehicle is calculated using assigned Aruco codes placed on the CTV at a specific location (see fig. 3). As we know the ID of the vehicle, the pose of the CTV can be retrieved via the location service. Using a transformation matrix the HoloLens can calculate the human workers absolute pose in the CTV's world coordinate system. Unfortunately, the absolute poses of the vehicles are not accurate.

Therefore, we use a fusion provider service on a designated hardware to estimate a more accurate pose depending on multiple calculated poses of different vehicles over time. This fused pose is send back to the HoloLens and is assumed to be the most accurate pose of the worker. For collision avoidance and reduction of path interference, the human agent of the HoloLens and the vehicle agents continuously

Fig. 3. CTV with virtual overlay on the Aruco code

Fig. 4. Domain Model of the human agent

exchange their poses and the human agent is providing the desired personal distance information of the human worker. The fused pose calculation could also be implemented on the HoloLens. However, for easy replacement of fusion algorithms and to allow the use of distributed intelligence, the fusion provider is running on additional hardware in the same network. Hence, only the fusion provider has to be updated and not the human agent of every single smart glass in the field has to be deployed.

B. Multi-Agent System Design

The system includes the entities CTV, Human Worker and Fusion Provider, each represented by software agents and being part of a multi-agent system. The agents exist in the same physical network and offer their services using zeroconf service discovery. Following [5] we adapted the three agents according to the concept architecture. In the Cyber Layer the worker agent represents the human worker with the smart glasses and offers the service that provides the calculated relative poses retrieved by the recognition of CTVs in the view field (see fig. 4). The CTV agent represents the CTV with its properties and the location service that is used by the fusion provider (see fig. 5). The third party needed for the system to work is the fusion provider that retrieves the relative pose of the worker agent, relates it to the absolute pose of the corresponding CTV and returning an estimated absolute pose to the human worker agent (see fig. 6).

C. Agent Design

The human agent is designed as a BDI agent with beliefs (location in the actual environment, location of surrounding

Fig. 5. Domain Model of the CTV agent

Fig. 6. Domain Model of the fusion provider agent

entities), desires (observation of personal distance, resolution of surrounding entities) and intentions (requesting entities to move back in case of personal distance infraction). It contains information on the dedicated person (name, unique id, working role, actual pose and actual task). Additionally, it provides capabilities like the ability to carry small load carriers of specific type or moving freely on the shop floor. As a result, the agent is able to represent the human worker with his features and capabilities. In the use case, the agent can detect multiple CTV in the HoloLens' view field and calculate the relative pose to it. It can forward all determined relative poses to the fusion provider and receive one fused pose in world coordinates in return. The fused pose will be displayed in the view field of the user. In case there are recognized CTV penetrating the personal distance, the agent is requesting these vehicle to move away from the user.

The CTV agent is designed as a model-based reflex agent, which is keeping its internal state, storing and updating information like actual pose. Besides that, it is able to publish its pose for other members in the multi-agent system. It contains information on the dedicated CTV (name, unique id, actual pose and actual transport task). Additionally, it provides capabilities like the ability to carry small load carriers of specific type or moving freely on the shop floor. As a result, the CTV agent can control the transport robot and make it navigate in a warehouse, bid for transport orders, fulfil these, estimate its pose and publish it on request.

The fusion provider agent is designed as a logical reflex agent, which is providing the service of fusing poses of several locatable entities to an absolute pose for the requesting entity. Firstly, it offers a service to retrieve multiple relative

Fig. 7. Visualization of the fused pose

poses of an instance in relation to other identified entities. Secondly, it is able to request absolute poses of any entity in the system. At last, it can use the relative and absolute poses for a fusion process and send the resulting fused absolute pose back to the requester of the first step. As a result, the fusion provider is able to help agents not capable of determining their own absolute pose in an environment to locate themselves and interact with other entities.

D. Measurements

For evaluating our system design, we have conducted a series of measurements. In the first test case, the human worker who is wearing the HoloLens is standing at a fixed position and looking at the CTV (actually the HoloLens is mounted on a tripod to avoid movement of the person while recording data). The human agents exchange localization information with the agents of those CTVs, which are in the field of view. Fig. 7 shows the visualized pose of the CTVs as well as the human worker pose. His line of gaze is pointing towards the CTV (see one red pole) and his height is visualized with an upright red pole. The orange circle around each CTV depicts the warning distance of the CTV pose. Further, the yellow circles with the black triangle are the calculated human worker pose according to the respective CTV. The fused pose of the worker conducted by the fusion provider agent is displayed as blue circle and a black triangle pointing into the direction, which faces the CTVs. The used fusion provider calculates the average of poses. However, the software structure allows easy replacement of the algorithm.

To determine whether the pose calculated by the fusion agents is more precise than the pose, which the human agent gets from one CTV agent, we have conducted a test scenario in which the HoloLens is fixed on a tripod stands at a fixed position and its gaze is pointing between both CTVs in a way that both Aruco codes are recognized. We have taken data readings in each of them the agent communicates with the fusion agent and determines its position. The position

Fig. 8. Calculated X-Coordinate of Human

Fig. 9. Calculated Y-Coordinate of Human

is given in x- and y-coordinates in the world coordinate system. Further, we have recorded the pose of the human worker, which each CTV calculates. Fig. 8 and fig. 9 show the calculated x- and y-coordinate of the human worker from CTV 1 and CTV 2 as well as the coordinates gained by the fusion agent and the mean coordinates in x- and y-axis, which can be referred to as the reference position.

One can see that the position calculated from each CTV are differing in x-coordinate with a maximum of 140 mm and in y-coordinate with a maximum value of 100 mm. This depends on the uncertainty of the pose of each CTV as well as on the precision of the pose of the marker identified on each CTV. Further, the readings according to CTV 2 are showing a larger variance. This may also depend on the identified marker position. Therefore, the absolute position calculated of the fusion provider is assumed to be the most accurate, although we are aware that errors of the poses of each CTV lead to an error in the calculated absolute pose of the human worker. We will discuss this circumstances in the outlook section. The following figure (see fig. 10) depicts readings that were taken while a user was wearing the HoloLens when walking around the two vehicles. During the test run, the user was looking at the vehicles in a way that both Aruco codes were tracked. The data shows a constant tracking of the position of the user. One can see the absolute positions of the two vehicles and the user.

Fig. 10. Calculated Position of Human

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper shows one step towards adaptive human-technology interaction in multi-agent systems for intralogistics. A human dedicated software agent was designed and implemented, that is able to make the human part of a technical system and interact on behalf of the human worker. It enables machines in the socio-technical system to be aware of humans in a way that the human's needs are taken into account and the robot's behavior adapts to them. The personal distance of the human and the footprint of the robots can be considered to keep distances between the actors. Although in the tested use case only one human worker and two CTV were sharing their workspace, the system uses a decentralized structure and therefore, it is scalable and not limited to the amount of humans and CTV working together. This allows the usage in complex environments which are usually found in intralogistics and manufacturing systems.

Thus, intralogistics transport tasks in partially automated systems, where robots act together with humans can predictively be optimized and stabilized. Using localization techniques and awareness of collaborating entities, not only intralogistics scenarios but also outdoor applications e.g. public transport use cases can benefit from this method.

V. OUTLOOK

The next steps in our evaluation are a better pose estimation, accuracy evaluation, the analysis of reaction of the humans on the actions of the robots in the process of adapting to personal distances. To estimate the human's position after loss of markers, the internal pose tracking of the HoloLens will be included and references on the last known marker position will be used to calculate a continuous pose estimation.

To improve the pose estimation, filters like EKF will be implemented and evaluated. For the evaluation of the accuracy of the system, we plan to use the reference tracking system of OptiTrack motion capturing system, which provides accuracies in submillimeter range. Future implementations will also include markerless vehicle identification to avoid additional effort in creation and implementation of artificial markers.

For better interaction, proxemics will be examined in more detail, so that also the intimate and social distance

are considered. It is imaginable that active communication between robots and humans may be initiated after entering the social distance or further safety protocols are being triggered in case the intimate distance is penetrated.

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